

PLANNING PERFORMANCE MONITORING AND STRATEGIC COLLABORATIVE LEARNING STRATEGIES FOR MANAGING NON-PROFESSIONAL TEACHERS IN PUBLIC SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN RIVERS STATE

Deborah Abraham OGOSU
Department of Educational Management,
Faculty of Education,
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the role of planning performance monitoring and strategic collaborative learning strategies in managing non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The research adopted a descriptive survey design to gather data from 350 principals of senior secondary schools, comprising 241 males and 109 females, using a census sampling technique. Data were collected through a self-constructed 10-item questionnaire titled Planning Performance Monitoring and Strategic Collaborative Learning Strategies for Managing Non-Professional Teachers Questionnaire (PPMDCLSMNTQ), validated by experts and tested for reliability using the test-retest method, yielding a Cronbach Alpha coefficient of .886. Out of 350 questionnaires distributed, 345 were retrieved, representing a return rate of 98.57%. Data analysis was conducted using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and independent sample t-test to test the hypotheses at a .05 significance level. Findings revealed that both planning performance monitoring and strategic collaborative learning, including peer observation programs, are significantly employed to manage non-professional teachers and enhance their professional competence and service delivery. The study concluded that systematic monitoring and collaborative learning initiatives are crucial for improving instructional effectiveness. The study recommended that school administrators should institutionalize structured performance monitoring systems and establish sustainable collaborative learning programs to maximize teacher performance in Rivers State.

Keywords: Non-Professional Teachers, Performance Monitoring, Collaborative Learning, Peer Observation, Service Delivery, Secondary Schools.

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INTRODUCTION

The effectiveness of secondary education depends largely on the competence, motivation, and professional capacity of teachers who serve as the primary agents of curriculum delivery and student development. In Nigeria, particularly in Rivers State, the presence of non-professional teachers getting involved in the business of teaching without requisite pedagogical qualifications has raised concerns about instructional quality and learning outcomes. Managing this category of teachers requires deliberate administrative interventions such as planning performance monitoring and strategic collaborative learning strategies that enhance their skills, professionalism, and commitment to effective service delivery (Okeke, 2020). As such, effective teacher management strategies are therefore indispensable in promoting instructional quality, accountability, and continuous improvement in the school system.

Planning performance monitoring refers to the systematic process of setting teaching performance goals, tracking progress, and providing constructive feedback to improve teacher effectiveness (Adu & Olaoye, 2019). In educational management, performance monitoring is essential for identifying areas of weakness, aligning teacher practices with institutional goals, and encouraging accountability. When well-planned, performance monitoring enables school administrators to evaluate non-professional teachers objectively, identify professional gaps, and design targeted interventions such as mentoring or capacity-building programs (Nwankwo, 2021). It also ensures that teaching standards are consistently maintained, leading to improved learning outcomes and the overall credibility of public secondary schools.

In the context of Rivers State, where the demand for qualified teachers often exceeds supply, non-professional teachers play a significant role in sustaining instructional delivery, especially in rural or underserved areas. However, their lack of formal teacher training often translates to limited pedagogical competence, classroom management difficulties, and inconsistent instructional quality (Eze, 2022). Planning effective performance monitoring mechanisms allows administrators to bridge these gaps by establishing clear performance expectations, setting measurable teaching targets, and implementing evaluation frameworks that promotes self-assessment and professional growth. This aligns with the principles of Goal-Setting Theory (Locke & Latham, 1968), which emphasizes that clearly defined goals and feedback enhance motivation and performance.

Beyond monitoring, strategic collaborative learning and peer observation programs are essential tools for managing and developing non-professional teachers. Collaborative learning involves structured opportunities where teachers share experiences, observe one another's practices, and reflect collectively on teaching methods. According to Adebola and Ijaiya (2020), peer collaboration promotes knowledge exchange, builds confidence, and strengthens professional relationships that support continuous learning. Through collaborative learning, non-professional teachers can acquire classroom strategies, improve instructional delivery, and internalize best practices from experienced colleagues. This process encourages teamwork and shared responsibility, key components of school effectiveness and performance improvement.

Furthermore, peer observation programs enhance reflective practice and professional dialogue among teachers. When teachers observe peers during classroom sessions, they gain insight into diverse teaching methods, instructional strategies, and classroom management techniques. This reflective engagement enhances their instructional competence and nurtures a culture of professional accountability (Ekpenyong, 2021). For non-professional teachers, peer observation serves as a practical avenue for learning and self-evaluation, complementing formal

professional development initiatives. Therefore, incorporating structured collaborative and peer learning programs in teacher management systems is crucial for improving instructional standards and service delivery.

Many public senior secondary schools struggle with inadequate teacher supervision, lack of structured professional development programs, and ineffective appraisal mechanisms (Ololube, 2017). Consequently, non-professional teachers often find their way into the education system and operate without sufficient guidance or professional growth opportunities (Adebayo & Ojo, 2020). According to Ololube (2006, 2011), the integration of planning performance monitoring and strategic collaborative learning provides a framework for continuous assessment, skill enhancement, and collective improvement, which are vital for effective school management. These strategies ensure that teaching practices remain aligned with educational objectives and national standards, even among untrained personnel.

Additionally, implementing such strategies aligns with Nigeria's broader educational reform agenda aimed at improving teacher quality and accountability across all levels of education. The National Policy on Education (FRN, 2014) emphasized the need for regular supervision, mentoring, and professional development to ensure that teachers remain competent and effective. Planning performance monitoring and strategic collaborative learning represent practical and sustainable management approaches for improving the competence of non-professional teachers in public senior secondary schools (Ololube, 2017). These strategies do not only promote professional growth and accountability but also contribute significantly to achieving quality education delivery.

According to Ololube (2017), education remains the cornerstone of national development, therefore, making it a priority enhances effective teacher management through planned monitoring and collaborative learning to help strengthen instructional capacity and ensure that secondary education system in Rivers State meet contemporary educational demands.

Statement of the Problem

The effectiveness of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State largely depends on the competence and professionalism of teachers who deliver classroom instruction. However, the persistent employment of non-professional teachers has posed a significant challenge to quality education delivery. Many of these teachers lack foundational knowledge in educational psychology, instructional methods, and classroom management, resulting in inconsistent teaching standards and poor student performance. Despite their contributions in addressing the issue of teacher shortages, their limited professional capacity undermines the attainment of educational objectives in the state.

Furthermore, the absence of well-structured planning performance monitoring mechanisms in many schools has compounded the problem. Without systematic goal setting, supervision, and feedback systems, non-professional teachers often receive little guidance or accountability for their instructional practices. Similarly, inadequate implementation of strategic collaborative learning and peer observation programs restricts opportunities for these teachers to learn from experienced professionals, share best practices, and improve their pedagogical skills.

Accordingly, there is a widening gap between teaching standards and desired learning outcomes in public senior secondary schools. The lack of coordinated management strategies for non-professional teachers continues to hinder effective service delivery, teacher motivation, and school performance. Therefore, the problem of this study is to determine the extent to which planning performance monitoring and strategic collaborative learning programs are utilized to

manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Aim and objectives of the study

The aim of this study was to examine the planning performance monitoring and strategic collaborative learning strategies for managing non-professional teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically the objectives are to:

- Investigate the extent planning performance monitoring is used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- Identify the extent organizing strategic collaborative learning and peer observation programs are used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

- To what extent is planning performance monitoring used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
- To what extent is organizing strategic collaborative learning and peer observation programs used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study at 0.05 level of significance:

- There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent planning performance monitoring is used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent organizing strategic collaborative learning and peer observation programs is used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Goal-Setting Theory

The Goal-Setting Theory developed by Edwin A. Locke (1968) and later expanded with Gary P. Latham (1990, 2002) is one of the most influential theories of motivation and performance management in organizational and educational settings. The theory posited that setting clear,

specific, and challenging goals enhances individual performance because such goals direct attention, mobilize effort, increase persistence, and encourage the development of strategies for task accomplishment (Locke & Latham, 2002). In essence, the theory emphasized that human actions are purposeful and guided by conscious goals, and that motivation arises when individuals commit to achieving desired targets.

Locke's early research established that specific and challenging goals produce higher levels of performance than vague or easy goals. For example, telling a teacher to "improve lesson delivery" is less effective than setting a goal such as "improve student engagement by incorporating at least two interactive learning activities per week." The specificity of the goal provides clarity and focus, while its difficulty stimulates commitment and effort. Furthermore, goals must be accompanied by feedback mechanisms to inform individuals about their progress, enabling them to adjust their strategies and sustain motivation (Lunenburg, 2011).

According to Locke and Latham (2002), five core principles underpin the Goal-Setting Theory: clarity, challenge, commitment, feedback, and task complexity. Clarity refers to the precision of the goal; challenge reflects its level of difficulty; commitment involves the individual's dedication to achieving the goal; feedback provides necessary information on progress; and task complexity considers the cognitive and practical demands required to achieve the goal. When these elements are aligned, performance tends to improve significantly.

In educational management, the Goal-Setting Theory is highly applicable to performance monitoring, professional development, and teacher management. School administrators can use this framework to set performance expectations, plan systematic monitoring programs, and ensure that teachers' especially the non-professional teachers understand what is expected of them, such as, planning performance monitoring activities like classroom observations, feedback sessions, and lesson evaluations aligns with the theory's emphasis on goal clarity and feedback. This process helps non-professional teachers recognize specific areas of improvement and track their professional progress over time (Locke & Latham, 2013).

Similarly, the theory provided a concrete foundation for organizing strategic collaborative learning and peer observation programs in schools. When teachers collaborate to achieve shared learning goals, they develop stronger professional networks, exchange effective teaching strategies, and increase motivation to meet performance standards. Collaborative goal setting also enhances mutual accountability, ensuring that all members of the teaching team contribute to collective objectives (Lunenburg, 2011). Through peer observation, teachers receive direct, constructive feedback, which helps them refine teaching practices, align with school goals, and improve instructional quality.

Moreover, the Goal-Setting Theory emphasizes the role of goal commitment, which is particularly relevant for managing non-professional teachers. Non-professional teachers often require additional support, mentoring, and feedback to build confidence and professional competence. Involving non-professional teachers in the school business administration's goal-setting processes like developing classroom management plans, instructional goals, or student achievement targets, school leaders will be able to increase their ownership of outcomes and intrinsic motivation. This participatory approach reinforces the principle that individuals are more likely to strive for goals they have helped to define (Locke & Latham, 2006).

Additionally, performance monitoring in schools can be framed within the feedback loop of goal setting. Feedback helps educators adjust their teaching methods, adopt innovative strategies, and sustain commitment to continuous improvement. When teachers observe measurable progress, it strengthens their sense of efficacy and encourages ongoing learning

(Kreitner & Kinicki, 2010). Thus, the incorporation of structured feedback sessions, regular evaluations, and peer discussions into the management of non-professional teachers certifies that professional growth is both measurable and motivational.

Therefore, Goal-Setting Theory provides a robust theoretical basis for understanding how clearly defined objectives, continuous feedback, and collaborative engagement can enhance performance among non-professional teachers in public senior secondary schools, and by integrating this theory into educational management practices, school administrators will be able to design effective performance monitoring systems, establish meaningful professional learning communities, and supports a culture of accountability and motivation. The application of Locke and Latham's (1968) principles guarantees that both teachers and institutions focus on measurable improvement, leading to enhanced service delivery and educational outcomes in Rivers State and beyond. Figure 1 provides a summary of the Goal-Setting Theory.

Figure 1: Summary of the Goal-Setting Theory

CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

Planning Performance Monitoring for Non-Professional Teachers for Effective Service Delivery

Teacher quality remains the determinant of educational outcomes in secondary schools. In Rivers State, the inclusion of those without formal teacher education qualifications has poses a major challenge to achieving consistent instructional standards and effective service delivery. To mitigate these challenges, school administrators adopt planning performance monitoring as a systematic strategy to assess, guide, and improve teacher effectiveness (Obioma & Amadi, 2021). This is so, because properly planned monitoring enables schools to identify performance gaps, establish clear teaching objectives, and promote accountability among both professional and non-professional teachers.

Performance monitoring involves setting performance benchmarks, observing classroom activities, and providing timely feedback to enhance teaching practices (Ogunyemi, 2020). For non-professional teachers, who often lack formal pedagogical preparation, this process serves as

a developmental tool that provides direction and clarity in lesson delivery. Planning ensures that monitoring activities are not arbitrary but strategically aligned with curriculum goals, school priorities and teacher needs (Igbinedion & Omoike, 2021). For instance, administrators can use observation checklists and self-assessment forms to track competencies in lesson planning, instructional strategies, and student engagement.

The process of planning performance monitoring drew support from Locke and Latham's Goal-Setting Theory (1968), which emphasizes the relationship between specific, challenging goals and improved performance outcomes. When non-professional teachers are involved in setting measurable teaching objectives, they become more committed to achieving them. A regular performance reviews and feedback sessions also provide opportunities for reflection and adjustment, ensuring that teachers remain focused on continuous improvement (Locke & Latham, 2002).

Moreover, performance monitoring plays an essential role in enhancing teacher accountability and professional growth. A planned approach ensures that evaluation outcomes inform capacity-building initiatives such as mentoring, workshops, or refresher programs (Okoro, 2022). Through ongoing assessment and targeted professional support, non-professional teachers can develop instructional competencies comparable to those of trained professionals. This not only improves classroom delivery but also raises the overall performance level of public senior secondary schools.

Effective performance monitoring also contributes to transparency and fairness in teacher evaluation. When monitoring processes are standardized and properly documented, they minimize bias and ensure that all teachers are assessed using the same criteria (Agabi & Emeh, 2020). Furthermore, consistent feedback helps teachers understand performance expectations and identify areas requiring improvement. Such transparency strengthens trust between administrators and teachers, nurturing a culture of cooperation and shared responsibility.

However, several challenges undermine the effective planning of performance monitoring systems in public secondary schools. These include insufficient training for school heads, limited administrative tools for data collection, and the absence of structured evaluation policies (Njoku & Onuoha, 2021). Consequently, monitoring is often irregular or subjective, reducing its developmental impact on non-professional teachers. To address these challenges, education authorities should institutionalize clear monitoring frameworks supported by regular supervision, data-driven evaluation instruments, and periodic training for administrators. Therefore, planning performance monitoring remains the basis for effective teacher management and instructional improvement in Rivers State's public senior secondary schools. Planning performance monitoring helps administrators set clear expectations, promote accountability, and guide non-professional teachers toward professional excellence.

Organizing Strategic Collaborative Learning and Peer Observation Programs to Manage Non-Professional Teachers for Effective Service Delivery

In recent years, the management of non-professional teachers in public senior secondary schools has become a pressing issue for educational administrators in Rivers State. These teachers, though valuable in bridging staffing gaps, often lack the professional training needed for effective instructional delivery. To enhance their competence and service delivery, school administrators must adopt strategic collaborative learning and peer observation programs as effective developmental strategies (Olawale, 2021).

Strategic collaborative learning encourages teachers to work together to improve their instructional practices through joint planning, shared reflection, and cooperative problem-solving. According to Alade and Adegbite (2020), collaboration among teachers promotes knowledge exchange and professional growth, particularly when it involves mentoring relationships between experienced and non-professional teachers. In such settings, non-professional teachers can learn through modeling, discussion, and peer feedback, which reinforces their pedagogical and classroom management skills.

Peer observation programs complement collaborative learning by allowing teachers to observe each other's classroom practices. This approach is rooted in Bandura's Social Learning Theory (1977), which emphasizes learning through observation and imitation. Non-professional teachers benefit by observing how experienced teachers handle lesson delivery, engage students, and evaluate learning outcomes. Structured peer observation promotes reflective practice, as participants analyze observed behaviors and apply learned strategies to their own classrooms (Iheanacho & Oboh, 2022).

Organizing such programs requires deliberate administrative planning. School leaders must create an environment that supports teamwork, openness, and continuous learning. According to Ajayi and Odu, (2021), successful collaborative learning depends on leadership support, a shared vision for professional improvement, and sufficient time allocation for meetings and peer observation sessions. School heads can organize learning teams, departmental clusters, or mentorship groups where professional and non-professional teachers exchange ideas and co-develop lesson materials.

Furthermore, collaborative learning and peer observation develops reflective practice, an essential component of professional growth. Teachers engage in post-observation discussions to review their teaching approaches, identify strengths and weaknesses, and plan improvements. This process enhances self-evaluation and promotes a sense of collective responsibility for educational outcomes (Mbah, 2021). For non-professional teachers, these interactions not only enhance technical teaching skills but also build confidence, collaboration, and adaptability in dynamic classroom environments.

In public secondary schools in Rivers State, supervision resources are limited, and peer observation serves as a cost-effective method of internal capacity building. When teachers learn from each other within the same school environment, the process becomes sustainable and contextually relevant (Obioma & Amadi, 2021). However, for these programs to succeed, there must be clear guidelines, administrative coordination, and institutional recognition of teachers' efforts. Incentives such as acknowledgment in staff meetings or inclusion in promotion assessments can motivate teachers to participate actively.

Strategic collaborative learning and peer observation programs represents practical approaches to manage and develop non-professional teachers. These initiatives promote shared learning, reflective practice, and teamwork, which collectively enhance teaching effectiveness and service delivery. A properly organized and supportive leadership can bridge the competence gap between professional and non-professional teachers, ensuring that all educators contribute meaningfully to achieving quality education.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design, which was aimed at gathering data from respondents based on their views and opinions to address the research questions. This design was

considered appropriate for examining how non-professional teachers are managed for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The population of the study consisted of all 350 principals of senior secondary schools in Rivers State, comprising 241 males and 109 females (Rivers State Senior Secondary Schools Board, 2024). Since the total population was relatively small, a census sampling technique was employed, allowing the researcher to include all 350 principals in the study.

The research instrument was a self-designed, 10-item questionnaire titled Planning Performance Monitoring and Strategic Collaborative Learning Strategies for Managing Non-Professional Teachers Questionnaire (PPMDCLSMNTQ). The instrument consisted of two sections: Section A captured the demographic information of respondents, while Section B contained items that elicited responses relevant to the research objectives. The questionnaire was structured on a 4-point modified Likert scale with response options ranging from Very High Extent (VHE = 4), High Extent (HE = 3), Low Extent (LE = 2), to Very Low Extent (VLE = 1).

To establish validity, the instrument was reviewed by the researcher's supervisor and two experts from the Department of Educational Management, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. Their suggestions and corrections were incorporated before the final administration. For reliability, a test-retest method was conducted using 20 principals from the study population who were not part of the main sample. After a two-week interval, the same instrument was re-administered to the same respondents to determine response consistency. The reliability coefficient, computed using Cronbach's Alpha, yielded an index of 0.886, indicating high internal consistency and confirming that the instrument was reliable for data collection.

A total of 350 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the principals with the assistance of two trained research aides. Respondents were encouraged to complete the questionnaires immediately to ensure a high response rate; however, some were allowed to submit theirs later, and follow-up visits were made to retrieve them. Out of the 350 copies administered, 345 copies were successfully retrieved and analyzed, representing a return rate of 98.57%.

For data analysis, the mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while the independent sample t-test was employed to test the null hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance using SPSS (Version 29). The decision rule for interpreting the mean scores was based on real limits of numbers: 3.50–4.00 (Very High Extent), 2.50–3.49 (High Extent), 1.50–2.49 (Low Extent), and 0.50–1.49 (Very Low Extent). For hypotheses testing, the null hypothesis was accepted if the Sig. (2-tailed) value was greater than 0.05 and rejected if it was less than 0.05.

This methodological framework ensured that the study produced valid, reliable, and empirically grounded findings on planning performance monitoring and strategic collaborative learning strategies for managing non-professional teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: To what extent is planning performance monitoring used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean ratings and standard deviation of the respondents on the extent planning performance monitoring used to manage non-professional teachers' for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

s/n	Item Statements	Male Principals' N=238		Female Principals' N=107		Mean Set		Decision
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
1	Regularly scheduled performance reviews create opportunities for professional growth for nonprofessional teachers.	3.15	.68	3.25	.59	3.20	.63	HE
2	Utilizing peer observations as part of performance monitoring promotes collaborative learning among non-professional teachers.	3.31	.49	3.29	.51	3.30	.50	HE
3	Performance monitoring promotes accountability among non-professional teachers in delivering quality education.	3.27	.65	3.22	.68	3.24	.67	HE
4	Coordinating performance monitoring facilitates timely feedback that helps non-professional teachers adjust their instructional strategies.	3.28	.55	3.24	.63	3.26	.59	HE
5	Performance monitoring allows for the identification of professional development needs among non-professional teachers.	3.23	.67	3.35	.58	3.29	.63	HE
Grand Mean & SD		3.25	.61	3.27	.60	3.26	.60	HE

Table 1 presents the mean ratings and standard deviation of the respondents on the extent is planning performance monitoring used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The analysis presented in the above table showed the following range perceptions for items 1 to 5: Regularly scheduled performance reviews create opportunities for professional growth for non-professional teachers (Mean=3.20 and SD=.63), Utilizing peer observations as part of performance monitoring promotes collaborative learning among non-professional teachers (Mean=3.30 and SD=.50), Performance monitoring promotes accountability among non-professional teachers in delivering quality education (Mean=3.24 and SD=.67), Coordinating performance monitoring facilitates timely feedback that helps non-professional teachers adjust their instructional strategies (Mean=3.26 and SD=.59), and Performance monitoring allows for the identification of professional development needs among non-professional teachers (Mean=3.29 and SD=.63). These indicated that the respondents' perceptions for items 1-5 showed a High Extent, as their mean ratings fall within the range of 2.50–3.49. Furthermore, the table showed a grand mean and standard deviation (Mean = 3.26 and SD = .60), which is above the criterion mean of 2.50, and the mean ratings fall within the range of 2.50–3.49. This further implies that, to a high extent, the planning performance monitoring was used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Question 2: To what extent is organizing strategic collaborative learning and peer observation programs used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean ratings and standard deviation of the respondents on the extent organizing strategic collaborative learning and peer observation programs used to manage non-professional teachers' for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

s/n	Item Statements	Male Principals' N=238		Female Principals' N=107		Mean Set		Decision
		Mean	SD.	Mean	SD.	Mean	SD.	
6	Organizing collaborative learning initiatives enhances the sharing of resources and teaching strategies among non-professional teachers.	3.28	.58	3.29	.56	3.29	.57	HE
7	Peer observation encourages reflective practice, helping non-professional teachers improve their instructional techniques.	3.33	.48	3.17	.63	3.25	.55	HE
8	Collaborative learning helps non-professional teachers develop problem-solving skills through group discussions and activities.	3.28	.58	3.30	.46	3.29	.52	HE
9	Peer observation allows non-professional teachers to gain new perspectives on curriculum implementation.	3.37	.47	3.35	.51	3.36	.49	HE
10	Collaborative learning programs can help non-professional teachers better understand their students' needs through shared experiences.	3.28	.57	3.30	.49	3.29	.53	HE
Grand Mean & SD.		3.31	.54	3.28	.53	3.30	.53	HE

Table 2 presents the mean ratings and standard deviation of the respondents on the extent is organizing strategic collaborative learning and peer observation programs used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The analysis presented in the above table showed the following range perceptions for items 6 to 10: Organizing collaborative learning initiatives enhances the sharing of resources and teaching strategies among non-professional teachers (Mean=3.29 and SD=.57), Peer observation encourages reflective practice, helping non-professional teachers improve their instructional techniques (Mean=3.25 and SD=.55), Collaborative learning helps non-professional teachers develop problem-solving skills through group discussions and activities (Mean=3.29 and SD=.52), Peer observation allows non-professional teachers to gain new perspectives on curriculum implementation (Mean=3.36 and SD=.49), and Collaborative learning programs can help non-professional teachers better understand their students' needs through shared experiences (Mean=3.29 and SD=.53). These indicated that the respondents' perceptions for items 6-10 showed a High Extent, as their mean ratings fall within the range of 2.50-3.49. Furthermore, the table showed a grand mean and standard deviation (Mean = 3.30 and SD = .53), which is above the criterion mean of 2.50, and the mean ratings fall within the

range of 2.50-3.49. This further implies that, to a high extent, the organizing strategic collaborative learning and peer observation programs were used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent planning performance monitoring used to manage non-professional teachers' for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 3: Summary of t-test analysis result on the significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent planning performance monitoring used to managed non-professional teachers' for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Respondents' Category	N(345)	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Decision
Male Principals'	238	3.25	.61	343	-.168	.244	Accepted
Female Principals'	107	3.27	.60				

Table 3 presents the summary of **t-test** analysis result on the significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent planning performance monitoring used to manage non-professional teachers' for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The result from the table shows a calculated t-value of -.168, with a significance level (p-value) of .244 at a degree of freedom of 343. Since the p-value is greater than .05, the result is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. This indicated that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent planning performance monitoring was used to manage non-professional teachers' for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent organizing strategic collaborative learning and peer observation programs used to manage non-professional teachers' for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis result on significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent organizing strategic collaborative learning and peer observation programs used to manage non-professional teachers' for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Respondents' Category	N(345)	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Decision
Male Principals'	238	3.31	.54	343	.596	.202	Accepted
Female Principals'	107	3.28	.53				

Table 4 presents the summary of t-test analysis result on the significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent organizing strategic collaborative learning and peer observation programs used to manage non-professional teachers' for effective

service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The result from the table shows a calculated t-value of .596, with a significance level (p-value) of .202 at a degree of freedom of 343. Since the p-value is greater than .05, the result is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. This indicated that there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent organizing strategic collaborative learning and peer observation programs were used to manage non-professional teachers' for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION

Planning Performance Monitoring for Non-Professional Teachers for Effective Service Delivery

Data from Tables 1 and 3 revealed to a high extent, the planning performance monitoring was used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, and there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent planning performance monitoring was used to manage non-professional teachers' for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

These findings are in line with the study of Obioma and Amadi (2021), who found that teachers' quality remain the determinant of educational outcomes in secondary schools, and the inclusion of those without formal teacher education qualifications has posed a major challenge to achieving consistent instructional standards and effective service delivery.

Igbinedion and Omoike (2021) study found that planning must ensures that monitoring activities are not arbitrary but strategically aligned with curriculum goals, schools main concern and teacher needs. The process of planning performance monitoring drew support from Locke and Latham's Goal-Setting Theory (1968), which emphasized the relationship between specific, challenging goals and improved performance outcomes.

Moreover, Okoro (2022) found that performance monitoring plays essential role in enhancing teacher accountability and professional growth. A planned approach ensures that evaluation outcomes inform capacity-building initiatives such as mentoring, workshops, or refresher programs. Through ongoing assessment and targeted professional support, non-professional teachers are able to develop instructional competencies comparable to those of trained professionals.

Agabi and Emeh (2020) found that effective performance monitoring also contributes to transparency and fairness in teacher evaluation. When monitoring processes are standardized and properly documented, they minimize bias and ensure that all teachers are assessed using the same criteria. They further noted that consistent feedback helps teachers understand performance expectations and identify areas requiring improvement. Such transparency strengthens trust between administrators and teachers, as well as nurtures a culture of cooperation and shared responsibility (Njoku & Onuoha, 2021).

Therefore, planning performance monitoring remains the basis for effective teacher management and instructional improvement in Rivers State's public senior secondary schools. Accordingly, planning performance monitoring helps administrators set clear expectations, promote accountability, and guide non-professional teachers toward professional excellence.

Organizing Strategic Collaborative Learning and Peer Observation Programs to Manage Non-Professional Teachers for Effective Service Delivery

Data in Tables 2 and 4 revealed to a high extent, the organizing strategic collaborative learning and peer observation programs were used to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, and there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent organizing strategic collaborative learning and peer observation programs were used to manage non-professional teachers' for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

These findings are in line with that of Alade and Adegbite (2020) that found that strategic collaborative learning encourages teachers to work together to improve their instructional practices through joint planning, shared reflection, and cooperative problem-solving. They further noted that collaboration among teachers promotes knowledge exchange and professional growth, particularly when it involves mentoring relationships between experienced and non-professional teachers.

In the same vein, Iheanacho and Oboh (2022) found that structured peer observation promotes reflective practice, because participants analyze observed behaviors and apply learned strategies to their own classrooms. Equally, Ajayi and Odu (2021) found that successful collaborative learning depends on leadership support, a shared vision for professional improvement, and sufficient time allocation for meetings and peer observation sessions.

Also, Mbah (2021) found that collaborative learning and peer observation promotes reflective practice, which are essential component of professional growth. This process enhances self-evaluation and promotes a sense of collective responsibility for educational outcomes. For non-professional teachers, such interactions do not only enhance technical teaching skills but also build confidence, collaboration, and adaptability in dynamic classroom environments.

To Obioma and Amadi (2021), they found that when teachers learn from each other within the same school environment, the process becomes sustainable and contextually relevant. Incentives such as acknowledgment in staff meetings or inclusion in promotion assessments can motivate teachers to participate actively.

CONCLUSION

This study has successfully examined the extent to which planning performance monitoring and strategic collaborative learning strategies are utilized to manage non-professional teachers for effective service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Findings from the study revealed that structured performance monitoring plays a critical role in guiding non-professional teachers, enhancing accountability, and improving instructional quality. Setting clear goals, providing regular feedback, and evaluating teaching practices, are able to make school administrators bridge the professional gaps that exist due to the lack of formal teacher training.

Additionally, the study established that strategic collaborative learning and peer observation programs are valuable tools for professional development. Collaborative learning promotes knowledge sharing, mentorship, and reflective practice, enabling non-professional teachers to adopt best practices from experienced colleagues. Peer observation encourages continuous improvement, enhances instructional competence, and promotes a culture of

professional accountability within schools.

Overall, the study concluded that the effective management of non-professional teachers requires the deliberate integration of both performance monitoring and collaborative learning strategies. These approaches not only improve teacher performance but also contribute to achieving quality service delivery in public secondary schools. The study highlighted the importance of proactive administrative intervention in promoting professional growth, ensuring accountability, and enhancing the overall effectiveness of the education system in Rivers State.

Recommendations

From the findings in this study, it is recommended that:

- School administrators in Rivers State should establish formal and systematic performance monitoring frameworks for non-professional teachers. This should include setting clear teaching goals, conducting regular classroom observations, providing constructive feedback, and implementing periodic evaluations to ensure continuous professional development and effective service delivery.
- Public senior secondary schools should organize structured collaborative learning initiatives and peer observation programs. These programs should facilitate mentorship, knowledge sharing, and reflective practice among teachers, enabling non-professional teachers to improve instructional competence, adopt best teaching practices, and enhance overall teaching effectiveness.

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